

ISic1027

I.Sicily inscription 1027

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140506

1. Ἔρωϛ □

2.

Edition: PHI175425

1. Ἔρωϛ □

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492655

EDCS 39102181

PHI 140506

PHI 175425

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0207 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5434

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.15

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